

Working paper: Shape optimization of interlocking joints

Shape and location of the joints can considerably change the mechanical behaviour of an assemblage of rigid or deformable blocks. The influence of bond pattern on the structural response of assemblies composed of conventional rigid blocks with flat faces have been extensively investigated.

SiDMACIB is one of the fewer research actions examining the influence of interlocking joint shapes on the structural resistance of a masonry assemblage. It extends the static problem of limit analysis to the non-planar joints and formulates this problem as a function of joint's geometric parameters.

This work presents SiDMACIB plugin, a CAD tool design to model structurally feasible single layer shells with arbitrary shapes composed of masonry interlocking blocks laid out with stacked or running bond pattern and with the possibility of having openings inside.

This Rhino-Grasshopper plugin has the following three main analytical components:

- 1) static problem component: it checks the feasibility of an interlocking model using limit analysis and concave method, and finds the stress state at the assemblage's joints;
- 2) infeasibility measurement component: it quantifies the infeasibility of an interlocking model designed by the user;
- 3) shape optimization component: it iteratively measures the assemblage infeasibility and automatically adjusts the interlocking joint shape to minimize and remove the structural infeasibility.

The plugin is developed using C# language and MATLAB's solvers as backends.

The extended static problem and the shape optimization are validated using the discrete element method by 3DEC applied to the interlocking helicoidal skewed arches, in collaboration with Prof. K. Bagi, from the Department of Structural Mechanics, Budapest University of Technology and Economics.

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Friction coefficient; Shear strength; Density

IOP	CFs	UV0IF
I1P		UV0Points
UVS0		UV1IF
WUS0		UV1Points
VWS0		WU0IF
UVS1		WU0Points
WUE0		VW0IF
VWE0		VW0Points
BP		Res
UV0LP		
UV1LP		
WU0LP		
VW0LP		
EF		
ET		
FC		
ShSt		
D		
OP		

3.1×10^{-9}